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THE CONSTRUCTION OF THE MODEL OF THE REGIONAL TRAP OF ABIOGENIC HYDROCARBONS IN THE CRYSTALLINE CRUST OF THE TRANSCARPATIAN DEPRESSION (Ukraine)

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Abstract

It is established thermobaric genesis and the corresponding features of the structure of the LVZs, their places and roles in the structure and geodynamics of the crust of the regions, in particular, Transcarpathia. It makes possible to clarify the geological and structural features of the crust of the region, to adequately interpret distribution of geophysical fields and decipher the peculiarities of local geodynamics and seismic-tectonic process, to clarify the level and nature of geo-ecological hazards, to more effectively predict and investigate deep spatial distribution of mineral resources.

Keywords: The Transcarpathian depression (Ukraine), low seismic velocity and density zones, petrophysical thermobaric modelling, thermobaric hydrocarbon traps.

Introduction. The organization of exploration works based on the organic hypothesis of the origin of oil removed for a long time from the sphere of oil and gas interest significant territories and volumes of the Earth's crust outside the sedimentary cover, where oil and gas deposits can be found. Recognition of the deep genesis of hydrocarbons and the formation of deposits due to their vertical migration along faults has very important practical consequences. Today, it is no longer possible to plan the search for oil and gas deposits without taking into account the possible abiogenic synthesis of hydrocarbons, degassing of the Earth, migration of deep fluids and gases, decompaction of certain horizons of the Earth's crust [11, 15, 16, 18, 26]. Detailed modeling of the deep geological structure of a specific region is necessary to explain the physical nature of velocity local anomalies and related prospects for hydrocarbon exploration and production. In this context, the most effective is the method of petrophysical thermobaric modeling (PTBM), when information on seismic sections of DSS, tectonics, geothermal, and physical properties of rocks is taken into account. Material composition modeling of the lithosphere is based on comparing the materials of the DSS with the data of the experimental study of the physical parameters of rocks at

high *PT* parameters. It confirmed the new hypothesis of decompaction of mineral matter of the Earth's crust of thermobaric origin at depths of 5-25 km, which is recorded by the DSS in the form of low velocity zones (LVZ) – the calculated wave and gravity fields coincide with the observed ones.

Geological interpretation of the PTBM results.

A comprehensive analysis of seismicity, geodynamics, volcanic activity and mineral deposits in the Ukrainian Transcarpathian depression (TD) is mainly based on new information on geological, geophysical, geodesic, structural and geomorphological studies [1, 6, 19, 20, 22, 23, 27].

The TD (Fig. 1) is the part of the Carpathian orogeny where the significant restructuring of the tectonic pattern took place at the turn of the Paleogene and Neogene periods that resulted in a significant difference in the Earth's crust structure of the region. Active post-Alpine tectonic processes caused the formation of both the depression itself and young volcanic features. The depression extends from the NW to the SE and consists of two major units (Fig. 1).

Fig. 1. Schematic maps of the regional tectonic units (a, b), location of the RP-17 seismic profile (a, b) and iso-lines of heat flow (b) [1, 19, 20, 22, 23]. CMB – Chop-Mukachivsky basin, VGVR – Vygorlat-Guta volcanic ridge, SB – Solotvinsky basin, MHL – Mid Hungarian line.

They are the NW Chop-Mukachivsky basin on the Central massifs of the Internal Carpathians and SE Solotvinsky basin superimposed on the flysch zone of the Outer Carpathians. These units are separated from each other by the Vygorlat-Guta volcanic ridge. The Chop-Mukachivsky basin descends, while elevation, horizontal movement and high seismicity are characteristic of the Solotvinsky basin [27]. Drilling data show that the basement of the Transcarpathian depression consists of the Paleozoic metamorphic schists, the Triassic dolomites and dolomitized limestones, the Upper Cretaceous marls and mudstones with sandstones and the Palaeogene sandy-clay formations [22, 23].

The Paleozoic sediments are exposed in the NW depression. The Cretaceous and Paleogene sediments crop out mostly in the south-east, in the Solotvinsky basin. Thus, from the north-west to the south-east the younger sediments gradually comprise the basement of the Transcarpathian depression where numerous faults, clearly registered by both geophysical and geological methods give rise to a complicated block nature of its structure [19, 20, 22, 23].

The block tectonics is a specific characteristic of the Chop-Mukachivsky basin while it is much less expressed in the Solotvinsky depression. Active vertical and horizontal movements and high seismicity can occur here [1, 6, 19, 20, 22, 23, 27]. Along the TD the RP-17 profile [1] revealed the following horizons (1) the sedimentary cover ($V_p=1,7$ to $4,8$ km/s), (2) the Mesozoic basement of the depression ($V_p=5,3$ to $6,0$ km/s) and (3) the Paleozoic basement ($V_p=6,0$ to $6,4$ km/s). Where V_p is elastic longitudinal waves. In the Solotvinsky basin Precambrian rocks (V_p of $6,2-6,5$ km/s) and the Conrad boundary ($V_p=6,6$ to $6,8$ km/s) are also delineated (Fig. 2). The velocities of $V_p=7,5-8,5$ km/s are

registered on the Moho discontinuity. The minimal thickness of the folded basement of the depression is 3 km in the SE Chop-Mukachivsky basin. It increases to 4,0-4,5 km in the Solotvinsky basin. The layer of “granitoids” is determined by the velocity of 6,1-6,4 km/s for the Horizon II at depths from 4,5 to 8 km. The LVZs (Horizon III-LVZ) with the velocity of 6,0-6,1 km/s are below situated below.

The seismic horizon IV (6,2–6,5 km/s) at depths of 6-14 km was earlier believed to be the Conrad boundary (V, K_2). However, is now interpreted to be LVZ of the thermobaric origin located at depths of 6-17,5 km [11]. The Horizon VI is the second LVZ with a velocity of about 6,4 km/s in the crystalline crust of the TD. This layer is located above the Moho discontinuity (Fig. 1, 2). Its velocity values are small for basic rocks. The explanation of the nature of the upper and lower LVZs is possible in analyzing HF in the TD. There are its stationary component and non-stationary anomalies due to geodynamic processes and the distribution of radiogenic heat sources and thermal parameters of the environment [6, 19, 20]. In the depressions of the TD HF varies from 90 to 120 mVt/m². The intensive anomalies (110 mVt/m²) occur along the Central TD. Temperatures are very heterogeneous laterally and vertically: 5 km – 85-150°C, 10 – 180-300, 20 – 300-470, 30 – 450-650, at the M – 600-800°C (Fig. 1, 2).

In order to model the petrophysical structural characteristics of Transcarpathian Depression deep horizons, we proposed petrophysical modeling techniques using experimental data on changes in the physical characteristics of rocks in various PT conditions of experiments corresponding to those for specific geological regions [11, 15].

Fig. 2. Seismic section of the Earth's crust and local earthquake hypocentres along the TD [1, 22, 23, 27]. 1 – refraction layers and velocities along them; 2 – reflection horizons and their numbers; 3 – Moho discontinuity; 4 – faults; 5 – earthquake focuses; 6 – seismic boundaries; 7 - hydrocarbon exploitation wells.

A sample of the rock in the experiment is like being “submerged” to the definite depth. This technique made it possible to obtain a large amount of information about the change in elastic-density parameters of the mineral substance with depth for specific regions in a

short period of time. Below is an optimal block diagram of small-scale petrophysical deep structural modeling (Fig. 3).

Fig. 3. Block diagram of small-scale petrovelocity deep structural modeling.

1) The study of structural and tectonic features of the region; selection of the main groups of rocks forming the geological environment; its further dismemberment into separate blocks; 2) the analysis of a priori geological and geophysical information, taking into account the data of the deep thermodynamic situation; 3) selection of a collection of rock samples of the studied region, including possible deep analogues (based on the information of blocks 1, 2); 4) the drawing up program variants of experimental study based on the prediction of the distribution with depth of P and T (based on geothermy and gravimetry materials) and their subsequent use in experimental studies of rock samples in high-pressure-temperature apparatus; 5) the study of elastic and density parameters in different thermobaric

conditions based on rock samples collections; 6) statistical processing and analysis of the results of laboratory experiments; 7) complex processing of petrological information and experimental data; the search for correlational dependencies between relevant parameters; drawing up work sheets or tables; 8) the analysis of materials of field geophysical observations (primarily DSS); the construction of high-speed cuts in blocks and layers along the corresponding profile; 9) comparing the results of laboratory petro-velocity PT studies with seismic information; complex primary interpretation; 10) construction of a lithological model of the possible distribution with depth of surface analogues of deep rocks based on a systematic analysis of relevant information (blocks 1, 2, 6, 7 and 9); 11) reconstruction

based on the lithological model (block 10) of petrovelocity sections (V_p , V_s) according to experimental data (blocks 6, 7); 12) construction of a density cross-section with subsequent cyclic correlation of anomalies of the gravity field with velocity and physical cross-sections; 13) creation and analysis of models of distribution with depth of elastic-density (Young's and shear modulus, Poisson's ratio, compressibility, etc.) of mineral matter by individual blocks; comparison with primary geophysical information; 14) the construction of complex petrovelocity sections, which are based on the data of experimental PT studies and information accumulated in 10-13 blocks [9].

Influence of PT -regimes on the elastic characteristics and density of rocks. We conducted long-term investigations of the experimental changes in velocities and densities with depth for rocks under PT

conditions relevant to specific regions and at specific depths. The study established the occurrence of the velocity inversion of elastic longitudinal waves and density (ρ) at different depths (H). With increasing depth (that is, with increasing pressure (P) and temperature (T) affecting the specimen of the rock), after some initial increase in V_p and ρ , their decrease is observed. Then the velocities and densities increase again (Fig. 4).

Thus, a low velocity zones are manifested on the $V_p=f(PT)=f(H)$ curves whose configuration and location correlate well with elastic anomalies registered by deep seismic sounding (DSS) information from the Earth's crust at depths of 3-25 km. The changes of $V_p=f(H)$ can also be obtained from measuring the isobars of velocities ($V_p=f(T)$ at $P=\text{const}$) and their isotherms ($V_p=f(P)$ at $T=\text{const}$).

Fig. 4. Changes of elastic longitudinal waves, density and porosity relationships with depth. 1 – evenly granular granites, 2 – porphyroid granites, 3 – trachytoid granites, 4 – rapakivi granites, 5 – plagiogranites, 6 – charnockitoides, 7 – diorites, 8 – anortozites.

Detailed studies showed that both methods of determining $V_p=f(H)$ plots give identical results [9]. Regardless of the methods of determining velocities using several PT programs or calculating the isobars and isotherms there is a threshold value of changes of the temperature with depth ($\partial T/\partial H$) when the anomalous elastic state of mineral matter arises – LVZs. The changes of velocity of elastic waves with depth (V_p) in the rock of constant mineral composition can be calculated by the ratio of $\frac{\partial V}{\partial H} = \left(\frac{\partial V}{\partial P}\right)_T \cdot \frac{\partial P}{\partial H} + \left(\frac{\partial V}{\partial T}\right)_P \cdot \frac{\partial T}{\partial H}$. The LVZs in the Earth's crust are determined by the assumption of $\left(\frac{\partial V}{\partial H}\right) < 0$. As far as $\left(\frac{\partial V}{\partial P}\right)_T$, $\left(\frac{\partial P}{\partial H}\right)_P$, $\left(\frac{\partial T}{\partial H}\right)$ are positive, $\left(\frac{\partial V}{\partial T}\right)_P < 0$, then to form a zone it is necessary to fulfil the assumption for absolute values:

$$\left| \left(\frac{\partial V}{\partial P}\right)_T \cdot \frac{\partial P}{\partial H} \right| < \left| \left(\frac{\partial V}{\partial T}\right)_P \cdot \frac{\partial T}{\partial H} \right| \quad (1)$$

In most cases, the change of the lithostatic pressure with the depth can be considered as a constant number. Therefore, $\left(\frac{\partial P}{\partial H}\right)$ is $0,24 \div 0,32$ kbar/km at depths from 3 to 40 km for ancient shields. The temperature gradient at these depths varies within the wide range (from 5 to $25^\circ\text{C}/\text{km}$) [15]. The relative increase of velocities with pressure under room temperature is

characterized by two intervals: $P=(0 \div 2)$ kbar is the interval of maximum increase of velocity, $P > 2$ kbar where the minimum velocity gradient is observed. As a rule, the velocity change with temperature under atmospheric pressure has three intervals: $T < 80 \div 100^\circ\text{C}$ (minimal changes), $T \approx 80 \div 250^\circ\text{C}$ (maximal changes).

Further heating within the interval of $T=250 \div 600^\circ\text{C}$ results in the small decrease of the velocity. The relative changes of velocity under compensating constant pressure (isobars) and constant external temperature (isotherms) are different in absolute values. Within the interval of $20 \div 70^\circ\text{C}$ under $P < 0,7$ kbar the changes of velocity with temperature are negligible, i.e. up to a depth of 2-3 km the velocities always increase intensively. It is caused by the growth of V_p with pressure due to induration of rocks. The interval $T=100 \div 250^\circ\text{C}$ is the interval of the most intensive changes of $V_p=f(T)$. Here decrease of velocity by two times is possible because of temperature influence under atmospheric pressure and by about 10-20% under compensating pressure of $P \approx 1,2 \div 3,5$ kbar; $T \approx 110 \div 250^\circ\text{C}$ that the greatest negative changes of velocity of the elastic waves are observed and zones of low velocities (LVZs) are revealed. The experiments found $\left(\frac{\partial V}{\partial T}\right)_P = -2,7 \pm 0,5$ ($P \approx 0,5$ kbar); $-0,7 \pm 0,3$ ($P=2$ kbar); $-0,33 \pm 0,1$ m/s $\cdot^\circ\text{C}$ ($P=5$ kbar) and V_p from pressure under different constant temperatures

$(\partial V / \partial P)_T = 0,8 \pm 0,3$ (pressure interval $0 \div 2$ kbar, temperature $20 \div 80^\circ\text{C}$); $0,01 \pm 0,005$ (under $P \approx 2 \div 5$ kbar, $T \approx 20 \div 80^\circ\text{C}$); $0,04 \pm 0,01$ (under $P \approx 2 \div 5$ kbar, $T \approx 265^\circ\text{C}$). Based on these data and experiments under the low and high-temperature regimes and calculations it was revealed that under low-temperature ($\partial T / \partial H < 9 - 11^\circ\text{C}/\text{km}$) the zones of the velocity inversion are not reflected on the curves of $V_P = f(PT) = f(H)$. In this case, the condition of (1) is not executed. If the temperature gradient is equal to $(\partial T / \partial H) < 15 - 20^\circ\text{C}/\text{km}$ in pressures interval of $1,8 \div 3,5$ kbar, the relationships of $V_P = f(PT)$ clearly revealed LVZs. The decrease in the velocities of different samples varies from 10 to 250 m/s in these zones.

Similar calculations were also performed according to experimental studies of rocks in various thermodynamic conditions of experiments performed by other authors [3, 4]. However, these data can be used for modelling only at depths more than 10-15 km.

Information on changes density vs. depth was obtained from studies of the volume decrement under PT -experiments and the ultrasonic determinations of the compressibility of the rocks (fig. 4).

The density characteristics of the rocks nonlinearly change with depth similarly to the elastic parameters. The $\rho = f(PT) = f(H)$ relationships demonstrate maximums and minimums. It implies that deep simultaneous influence of P and T on mineral matter results in the formation of zones of density inversion. This mechanism for the origin of the LVZ is corroborated by studies of rock density under programming influence of P and T . As it was expected, under PT relevant to the LVZs density also decreases. The values of $\partial \rho / \partial H$ sometimes are negative reflecting a considerable density decrease of rocks that creates zones of low density in the crust. Under thermodynamics conditions at 5-15 km depth the gradient of the density increment falls to zero or becomes negative (Fig. 2). The additional experiments show that the LVZs depend weakly on a mineral composition of the crust matter. Obviously, the structural transformations and chemical composition play a key role in the variations of rock density.

The low density is very sensitive to the temperature conditions of the Earth's crust similarly to the LVZs. Increasing deep HF decreases rock density, activates capability to decrease the rock density and increase their permeability and hygroscopicity (activates a process of fluid movement) that, for example, causes metamorphic transformation of rocks. In other words, these LVZs are to be the most active horizons of present-day geological-geophysical transformations of the crystalline crust mineral environment [9-11, 15, 13]. A multidisciplinary analysis of DSS data, geothermal and petro- structural modelling showed that the crystal domains of higher temperature gradients are distinguished by more complex character of variations in seismic velocity with depth. Here intensive LVZs occur [11, 15]. In "colder" crystal domains the thickness of the LVZs is negligible or zones are absent at all. In addition, we confirmed that the variations in the mineral composition of the rocks at depths of 5-20 km influence negligibly on position of LVZs and their intensity.

The comprehensive experiments on rocks and minerals under different PT -conditions disclosed an increase in relative deformation of grains and their twinning in the LVZs (5-15 km depth). The density of rocks increases inside the blocks of dislocations and decreases on intergrain boundaries. The defects of minerals packing increase. The intergrain boundaries expand due to their mylonitization, the amount of main micro fissures increases. There is depressurizing or opening of the gas-liquid inclusions in minerals in heating because of excess inner pressure. Moreover, the rocks are characterized the lowered density (Fig. 4) [9, 10, 12].

The petrophysical thermobaric modelling of the crystalline crust on the Ukrainian Shield (USh) demonstrated that characteristics of low velocity zones (LVZs) depend slightly on mineral composition of rocks at relevant depths. They are mainly related to the geothermal regimes of the crystalline crust in study areas [11, 15]. Being large-scale systems of transcrustal deep distortions, zones of low elastic properties and densities are the most permeable for ascending hydrothermal solutions and fluids of the mantle origin during the activation of tectono-magmatic processes accompanied with intensive heat flow (HF). Different processes of metasomatism, formation and localization of mineral resources (e.g. hydrocarbons) most likely occur in these zones. A satisfactory coincidence was obtained between the position of LVZs (decompaction zones) and mineral deposits in the Kirovograd ore region of the USh, on the NW Black Sea shelf, in certain areas of the Caspian Sea [11, 15, 16, 17, 26]. It follows that LVZs of the thermobaric nature serve as the diagnostic indicator of deep mineral deposits.

The LVZs in the crystalline crust as zones of increased porosity of mineral matter. The physical parameters of different types of crystalline (igneous and metamorphic) rocks are mainly controlled by the composition and structural-textural peculiarities of mineral material although a jointing and porosity (n) of the rocks, the state of intergrain boundaries also influence these characteristics. The occurrence of different types of pores and fissures is governed by the conditions of their formation and subsequent processes of transformations. Porosity in the crystalline rocks became the subject of the intensive studies due to examining migration of gas-liquid flows, particularly hydrocarbons, at different depths in the lithosphere [5, 8, 9-11, 28]. Based on the studies of the relationship between porosity and velocity under high PT in the granite samples from the USh, it became possible to characterize more clearly changing porosity and jointing vs. PT environments at different depths. The study also explains some crustal decompaction anomalies of rocks which, in turn, can act as migration pathway for hydrocarbons of the mantle origin. Under atmospheric pressure the clear nonlinear relationship is revealed between the velocity and porosity for 3 groups of the granites which differ in a grain size of rock-forming minerals. The gradients of changing $V_P / f(n)$ increase with increasing the size of grains (Fig. 5).

Fig. 5. Changes in velocity and pore space with pressure in granites. a – Change of $V_p=f(n)$ for granites: 1 – fine-grained, 2 – medium-grained, 3 – coarse-grained; b – change of mean values velocity of longitudinal waves for the medium-grained granites vs. pressure ($V_p=f(P)$) and porosity ($V_{pn}=f(n)$); c – relative change of pore space under the increase of pressure in granites: 1 – fine-grained, 2 – medium-grained, 3 – coarse-grained.

$$\text{The } \frac{n_0 - n_p}{n_0} = \frac{\Delta n}{n_0} = f(P) \text{ plots characterize}$$

the relative change in the pore space (in %) vs. pressure

in the granites, where $n = n_0 \left(1 - \sqrt{\frac{V_p - DP - V_0}{V_E - V_0}} \right)$,

D is the relative change in the velocity vs. pressure plot on the linear segment due to the elastic deformation of the rock-forming minerals (Fig. 5, c).

The given ratio makes it possible to estimate changes in the size of the pore space of rocks depending on the applied pressure (depending on the depth) and temperature, based on the data of the measurement of the speed of the propagation of elastic waves in rocks at different depths together with the change in the density of rocks in different PT conditions (fig. 5, c). In the low velocities zone (4–15 km) (the zone of decompaction of rocks, loosening of intergrain boundaries), an increase in porosity is observed.

In the crystalline crust, rocks are subject to compression, heating up, various structural and sometimes material transformations resulting from the action of pressures and temperatures. Heating causes an increase in rocks volume. The coefficient of volumetric thermal expansion of rocks: $2 \cdot 10^{-6}$ – $4 \cdot 10^{-4} \text{ K}^{-1}$; the average $3 \cdot 10^{-5} \text{ K}^{-1}$. When the rocks are heated to 300°C , we observed an increase in the volume of mineral matter by 1–1,5% and a corresponding decrease in density [9, 12, 13]. The action of high pressure, as a rule, leads to compression of the substance, the value of which is determined by compressibility or the coefficient of comprehensive contraction. At a depth of 5–10 km, the

pressure of $P=2,5$ – $3,0$ kbar can increase the crystalline rock densities by no more than $\sim 0,5\%$.

Thus, thermodynamic forces that facilitate the development of local high microstresses will predominate at depths from 3 to 10 km, causing volumetric destruction of structural integrity of the rocks, that results in the formation of deconsolidation of Earth's crust mineral matter at these depths [9, 12, 13]. In this PT interval in the crystalline rocks, a substance decomposes due to the internal multi-oriented stresses, which in local mineral contacts reach values exceeding the strength of individual minerals. This results in a fragile micro-destruction of the environment. The number of main microcracks increases (loosening). At the same time, the migration of free liquid and gas through micro-disruption of minerals and inter-grain contacts activates in the intergranular space, destroying the rock and forming secondary pores and cavities in it. This is a key process for the movement of deep fluids through rocks in the LVZs under natural conditions. In the LVZs, an increase in porosity is observed by 10–25% compared with values at depths of overlying layers (Fig. 6).

Decreasing the velocity of the elastic waves and changing in the density suggests that porosity increases by 10–20% in the LVZs at a depth of 4–15 km in a comparison with that at the 3–5 km depth (horizons of maximum elastic parameters above the LVZs). In the zones of decreased porosity (LVZs) intensive processes of mass transfer, gas-liquid including deep hydrocarbons seem to be the most intensive [9, 25].

Based on the foregoing, graphical presentations and theoretical calculations demonstrate that the rock porosity decreases by 30–50% at a 3–5 km depth (Fig. 6).

Fig. 6. Change in porosity of the crystalline rocks under thermodynamic conditions at the different depths.

A comparison of experimental data and geophysical observations. The DSS studies revealed anomalies of elastic behaviour of mineral matter in the form of LVZs (Fig. 4). They were also registered during the laboratory experiments on the rock samples simulating thermobaric parameters relevant to 3-25 km depths. A comparison of interdisciplinary experimental and field data allows us to put forward several ideas on the physical nature of elastic zoning mineral matter in the upper layers of the crystalline crust [9, 15].

Model and natural processes or phenomena are considered to be similar if their determining criteria are numerically equal. The theory of dimension and similarity makes it possible to use effective methods of selecting necessary relationships [9].

The criteria of similarity (C) are dimensionless quantities which characterize the given phenomenon or process. The similarity analysis was applied to select the dimensionless quantities which mostly control the velocity of the elastic wave in mineral matter. As the velocity mostly reflects the physical state of matter under different thermobaric conditions, it functionally depends on pressure (P), temperature (T), density (ρ), volume (U), specific heat capacity (C_{ou}) and the Poisson coefficient (σ)

$$V = f(P, T, \rho, U, C_{ou}, \sigma) \quad (2)$$

As objects under study have finite dimensions and are subjected to changing PT environments, it is reasonable to consider depending V on changing PT-regimes with a depth. Substituting T and P by their gradients (grad T and grad P), we shall get the following dimensions: [V]=m·s⁻¹; [grad P]=kg·m⁻²s⁻²; [grad T]=°C·m⁻¹; [ρ]=kg·m⁻³; [U]=m³; [z]=m; [C_{ou}]=m²·s⁻² (°C)⁻¹; [σ] - dimensionless.

Solving the matrix of their dimensions we shall obtain the followings criteria of similarity:

$$C_1 = \frac{gradP \cdot z}{V^2 \cdot \rho} \quad (3)$$

$$C_2 = \frac{gradT \cdot z \cdot C_{ou}}{V^2} \quad (4)$$

The first (C₁) characterizes the influence of pressure on the velocity of the elastic wave of the object of study within a boundary thickness of z, the second (C₂) characterizes the influence of temperature. Consequently, if a model (m) and its natural (n) affinity consist of the same matter and ρ_m=ρ_n and C_{oum}=C_{oun},

equality of the velocity in the model and natural settings will occur in satisfying the following condition:

$$gradP \cdot z = inv, \quad gradT \cdot z = inv, \quad (5)$$

where inv is invariant.

Based on these criteria of similarity, equality of mean values of P and T in the model and natural environments is enough to compare the velocity in these both settings. It implies that the V_p/V_s ratio (C₃) must be constant. The mean value of this ratio for the Earth's crust is 1,77 while its laboratory mean value is 1,8±0,1 with 0,95 confidence interval [15]. It follows that the C₃ criterion is the invariant number, e.g., it is numerically equal in nature and models. Therefore, the velocity of elastic wave in the relevant model must not differ from that in natural conditions. Accordingly, the scale coefficients can be taken to be equal to 1. The equations of the relationships between V_p, X1, P and T from experiments are invariant and can be applied without changes in simulating natural environments at different depths. Generally, the essence of the petrovelocity thermobaric modelling is the comparability of elastic wave velocity in the lithosphere from DSS method and experimental measurements of this parameter under high PT regimes pressures [9, 15]. From it follows that the LVZs at 3-25 km depth are most likely to be of thermobaric origin.

The nature of LVZ along the DSS profile (RP-17) using the PTBM methodology. The PTBM allows us to explain the origin of the LVZ along the profile [9-12, 13, 14, 18]. For this purpose, the samples are selected of slates, quartzites, metaconglomerates, mylonites, granite-gneisses, diorites, gabbroides and basalts from the USh and Transcarpathia because they seem to form the deep horizons of the TD. Their elastic characteristics were studied in detail at relevant PT conditions [9-12, 13, 14, 18] at low-temperature regime of the Chop-Mukachivsky portion of the profile (Fig. 7, a). In constructing models of other parts of the profile with high-temperature regime (abnormally high for the territory of Ukraine), temperature corrections were made for the values of velocities of the relevant rocks. For depths of 10-35 km relationships of V_p=f(PT)=f(H) were obtained applying isobars and isotherms of velocities obtained by the authors of this study, as well as data on rocks forming the deep horizons of the Earth's crust [3, 4]. As an example of such a modelling, for the area around 105 km of the RP-17 DSS profile, Figs. 7

a, b, c, and d demonstrate the data on temperature regimes, seismic velocities, calculated $V_p=f(PT)=f(H)$. A model is also presented for the distribution of mineral

environments with depth corresponding to these velocities. Having analyzed these materials, we made an assumption about the nature of the LVZs zones in the TD.

Fig. 7. Elements of PTBM for areas of 35, 75, 105 km of the RP-17 DSS profile (a-d) and the model of rocks distribution with a depth along TD (e) (this study and data from Chekunov et al., 1969; Tretyak et al., 2015; Nazarevich, Nazarevich, 2004; Nazarevich et al, 2002, 2011). a – temperature regimes; b – seismic velocity; c – calculated $V_p=f(PT)=f(H)$ for thermal regime of 105 km; d – distribution models for mineral materials vs. depth according to these velocities. 1 – refraction layers and velocities along them; 2 – reflection horizons and their numbers; 3 – Neogene layer; 4 – folded basement; 5 – Paleozoic amphibolite facies (gneisses); 6 – Proterozoic (Precambrian) gneisses with LVZs; 7 – basic rocks; 8 – crust-mantle mixture; 9 – Moho discontinuity; 10 – faults; 11 – earthquake focuses; 12 – seismic boundaries; 13 – hydrocarbon exploitation wells; 14 – LVZs; 15 – fluid flows.

In the TD (Fig. 7, d), the upper LVZ-I resulted from high T in compared with its average values due to radiogenic heat generation of clays, siltstones, sandstones, granite-gneisses and with some contribution of mantle heat [6]. In the LVZ-I the temperature varies from 160 to 260°C, therefore, this zone is of the thermobaric nature [11] and consists of decompaction granite-gneiss with schists which are vulnerable to destructive external influences.

Below the LVZ-I the temperatures are low because of the decrease in radiogenic heat. Besides, the mantle component of HF is controlled by the physical state of the underlying rocks that causes the formation of a layer with high velocity because of the dominance of P over T . This horizon consists of basic rocks. At depth of 18-26 km temperature regimes produced a new LVZ-II. The input of heat from the mantle warms up the rocks up to 600°C at 18-26 km depth (Fig. 7, d). The zone is composed of diorites, gabbroides, basalt-

ides and other products of volcanic activity. The ruptured structure of Moho allows us to suppose the occurrence of crust-mantle mixture here [14].

There are two voluminous domains in the LVZs along the profile. The first occurs in the Vygorlat-Guta volcanic ridge area which is apparently related to an intense inflow of mantle heat along the fault. The second one is located at a 90-120 km depth. The Chop-Mukachevsky basin is localized within the Transcarpathian mantle fault zone where volcanism was widespread. It now descends due to the powerful cooling of volcanogenic formations of low elastic parameters in the lower crust [6, 27]. Additional decompaction of basified formations above the Moho discontinuity and the velocity decrease are associated with shear stresses directed along the TD [27] which causes the dilatant decompaction of rocks [24].

Higher pressure ceases the growth of the zone due to the compensating effect of structural distortions under pressure. Thus, the zone modifies the configuration:

its thickness can be increased due to the increase of intensity of deep HF or the zone can disappear in case of lowering it. Such an instability of the thermodynamics of the LVZs causes their episodic occurrence in the Earth's crust as well as their vertical and horizontal migration depending on of the temperature variations in the deep horizons of Earth [9-11, 15, 28].

The seismic K_2 boundary seems to be thermobaric in origin which results from the intensive increase in V_p above the LVZ. However, it is not excluded that the intensive increase in the velocity above the LVZ can also be associated with occurring of the high velocity rocks instead if low velocity ones. In this case the deep thermobaric conditions facilitate a higher velocity jump.

An intense warming up of the rocks zone is a characteristic of in Sotolvinsky basin, which formed a large LVZs above the M discontinuity (in turn, here the latter ascends to 18-21 km). The constant heat inflow from the mantle heats the rocks at depths of 13-18 km and a new LVZ-II zone is formed. Some contribution to the increase in T in the zone is made by the rocks of low thermal conductivity of the LVZ-I above the zone LVZ-II that reduces the outflow of the mantle heat from the LVZ-II.

This is the region of transition from acidic rocks to rocks of intermediate composition, and gabbroids and diorites seem to underlain it. There is the development of LVZs in the Earth's crust in active zones of quite intense stresses. In the process of destruction of the mineral matter at certain depths, the development of LVZs can be associated with the action of the dilatancy effect [21, 24]. Theoretically, it means the linear proportionality of inelastic increases in volume and shear, or in other words the volumetric and shear inelastic deformations are functions of pressure and tangent stress. In crystalline rocks, the effect of the development of microcracks is manifested when the stresses satisfy the criterion for the onset of dilatant pre-destruction or, more simply, the elastic limit. It is assumed that the characteristic changes of types of brittle fractures observed in laboratory experiments on rocks, occur within the crust. On this basis the relevant models are developed for defects of the deep horizons of the crust. A certain disadvantage of our model is the requirement of the presence in the Earth's crust of shear stresses that reach the strength limits of the rocks. However, these phenomena are possible for the territory of Transcarpathia under study. Additional decompaction of basified formations above the M discontinuity and reduction of the velocity are associated with dilatant decompaction of the rocks due to shear stresses directed along the TD and the presence of the mantle Transcarpathian fault [2, 27]. Moreover, earthquakes are concentrated at a shallow depth of the TD (Fig. 8, d), which, in our opinion, is closely associated with the thermobaric zones of the upper crust decompaction. Here, the seismic activity

contributes to the widening of the channels for motion of fluid from the asthenosphere lens below the Carpathian region, which is described in [2, 7].

Elastic characteristics of the mineral substance along the DSS profile (RP-17). The elastic characteristics of a mineral substance in PT conditions are a source of important information about the action of internal stresses in the crust and qualitatively determine the intensity of the development of decompaction and fragile and plastic deformations in it. At depths of 5-15 km of the Earth's crust with increased heat flows, which are not provided with the necessary pressure compensation, destructive temperature stresses occur in the sample. This leads to the decompaction of rocks, a decrease in V_p and, as a result, a of low seismic velocity zone (registered by DSS) and anomalous behavior of rock modules appears at these depths. For isotropic media, modules can be calculated from $V_{p,s}$ and their density. In stationary isotropic conditions, solids can be roughly divided into plastic and fragile. When P and T influence them, their transition from one state to another is possible. Poisson coefficient is an indicator of these processes. Conventionally, for most fragile materials, $0,10 < \sigma < 0,25$, and for ductile materials, $0,25 < \sigma < 0,47$. If it is deformed and heated, inelastic phenomena develop in the substance, then the values can go beyond these limits up to negative values. Inelasticity, as a rule, appear itself in the form of fragile fracture or flow. From these positions, we qualitatively characterized the fragile and plastic state of the rocks of the upper horizons of the Earth's crust on the basis of thermobaric petrophysical modeling, which actually exists in the depths of the TD.

The depression extends from the NW to the SE and consists of two major units (Fig. 8, a).

They are the NW Chop-Mukachivsky basin on the Central massifs of the Internal Carpathians and SE Sotolvinsky basin superimposed on the flysch zone of the Outer Carpathians. These units are separated from each other by the Vygorlat-Guta volcanic ridge. The Chop-Mukachivsky basin descends while elevation, horizontal movement and high seismicity are characteristic of the Sotolvinsky basin.

According to DSS data (RP-17), PTBM was carried out along the TD. The simulation results are presented for the individual structures of the above-mentioned TD (pickets by profile P-35 CMB, P-75 VGVR, P-115 SB). Fig. 8, b, c, d show the average calculated values according to the V_p , V_s experimental data and density and values of the corresponding modules of rocks (G – shear modulus, σ – Poisson coefficient, β – compressibility).

In the LVZ, the upper horizons are composed of unconsolidated rocks and are homogeneous in terms of elastic parameters. With depth, they become fragile, with high compressibility (Fig. 8).

Fig. 8. a – the layout of the seismic profile (RP-17) and heat flows in the Transcarpathian depression; b, c, d – RP-17 sections (35, 75, 105) – horizons and structures according to the data of DSS and PTBM and corresponding modules (notational designations – see Fig. 7).

Below them, at depths from 4,5 to 8 km, there are layers of “granite-gneiss”. Here, crustal of low seismic velocities zones were discovered, where the temperature varies from 160 to 260°C. Therefore, the zone has a thermobaric nature [9-11] and it is composed of thermally decompacted granito-gneisses and slates, which are exposed to destructive external influences. This is indicated by the calculated modules (Fig. 8 b, c, d). At depths of 6-12 km, σ and β are decrease, G , β are increase slightly, rocks acquire quasi-fragile properties. The seismic horizon at depths from 6 to 17,5 km is composed of rocks of medium composition, and as the depth changes, σ and β acquire increased values in all three sections of the TD. This horizon is composed of rocks in a quasi-plastic state. The second layer is the LVZ in the crust of the TD with a velocity of about 6.4 km/s and located above the M boundary at a depth below 18-26 km and caused by temperature conditions (Fig. 8, c, d). The influx of heat from the mantle heats rocks $H=18-26$ km to 600°C (Fig. 2, 7). The zone is composed of diorites and basaltoides. LVZ-2 along the profile has two volumetric areas – the first in the VGVR area, associated with an intense influx of mantle heat along the fault [3]. The second area is located in the area of pickets 90-120 km (Fig. 8, d). The SB is characterized by the heating of the rocks that formed the continuous LVZ and intense seismic activity. According to the DSS, the M border has been raised to 15-21 km. However, it is possible that it is not clearly defined enough, perhaps the profile entered the large zone of the Transcarpathian deep fault. The rocks here are of a more fragile state (Fig. 8, d). This is connected with the development here of a system of macrocracks at significant shear stresses that exceed the elastic limit of

rocks at these depths, as evidenced by the low values of σ and G modulus. The appearance of auxetics at these depths is possible. The decompaction of basaltic formations above the M boundary is provoked by the dilatational loosening of the rocks, due to the action of shear stress directed along and across the depression and mantle Transcarpathian deep fault (Fig. 2, 7). Therefore, a mass of earthquake epicenters is concentrated at a shallow depth of the TD (Fig. 7), which, in our opinion, is closely related to the thermobaric zones of decompaction of the upper crust, their low elastic characteristics and σ values. Seismic activity contributes to the effect of expanding the channels of fluid movement [12], under the action of which the disintegration of the mineral substance of the TD is activated. Under thermodynamic conditions, which correspond to the LVZs at depths from 3-5 km to 12-20 km, changes are observed in the rocks, when their cataclastic transformation takes place with an increase in the cracking and porosity of the rocks [9, 11, 14, 18]. The migration of free water and gas through the microcracks of the rock is activated, destroying it, forming secondary cracks and caverns. At the same time, a so-called “degassing pipe” is formed, which is a source for the accumulation of abiogenic hydrocarbons in the crust, which under certain conditions (high pressure, decompression) penetrate into the near-surface horizons of the sedimentary cover, where explosive deposits are formed.

It has been shown for the first time, that the LVZs in the Earth’s crust (the region of thermobaric decompression of mineral matter) are its integral part (especially, in areas of the present-day and ancient geodynamic activation, accompanied by the increased deep

heat flows), providing the lithosphere stability. The study showed that the active heating of the Earth's interior inevitably causes the development of the LVZs, as a result of mantle cataclysms and the localization of radioactive elements. The horizons of thermobaric decompression of the rocks, which under the influence of stresses, multidirectional deformations and vibrations acquire the properties of strongly dislocated media, form vast migration channels of fluids, "degassing pipes". In turn, they provide the movement of useful mineral matter to the surface and also provoke intense relaxation of tectonic stresses, in particular, in the form of earthquakes. At present, when interpreting geophysical survey materials, it is necessary to take into account the presence of crustal thermobaric decompression zones (LVZ). In our view, such zones are almost worldwide occurrence in the Earth's crust. This changes outdated ideas on the geological and structural features of the regions under study.

The results of the studies give an opportunity to clarify the geological and structural features of the structure of the Earth's crust of Transcarpathia, to adequately interpret the spatial distribution of geophysical fields and to decipher the features of local geodynamics and seismotectonic process, to clarify the level and nature of geo-ecological hazards, to more effectively predict and study deep regional distribution of mineral resources.

Conclusions. The LVZs are the most active horizons of the present-day transformation of the mineral environment and changes in the structural features of the Earth's crust. The LVZs in the crystalline crust are its integral part stabilizing the lithospheric state. In our opinion, active heating of the Earth's interior, as a result of mantle cataclysms and the localization of radioactive elements, inevitably facilitates the formation of the LVZs which are the horizons of thermobaric decompression of the rocks. Such zones under the influence of fluid migration, stress, multi-directional deformations and vibrations become strongly dislocated media, provoking intense relaxation of tectonic stresses in the form, for example, of earthquakes. In turn, seismic activity causes widening migration channels for the mantle fluids producing the so-called "degassing tubes". Such tubes are the essential elements of the formation of hydrocarbon accumulations.

Based on geological-geophysical data, geodynamic researches and PTBM the TD is considered to be a region of the present-day active geological processes where mineral deposits are formed and earthquakes occur. Among known deep anomalies of the geophysical fields, LVZs are the most accessible to study using different geological-geophysical methods, including superdeep drilling. Taking into consideration the present analysis of the nature and origin of LVZs in the crust of Transcarpathia, it is possible to fulfil the most detailed and perspective study aiming at searching for mineral resources and clarifying the deep structure of the Earth, as well as explaining and predicting crustal earthquakes. Detailed further study of the deep structure of the TD and especially the position of the LVZs can significantly expand the possibilities for hydrocarbons

searching. Moreover, legends in Fig. 8 show hydrocarbon fields.

The LVZs are also domains of intensive relaxation of stresses of tectonically-active processes due to weakened elastic properties of their rocks. Here, act mechanisms for dilatancy destruction of the mineral environment at certain depths of the crystalline crust. Thermobaric LVZs (area of the lowered elasticity, density and increased porosity of rocks) are the trigger mechanism for the origin of earthquake and faults of different orientation in the Earth's crust that is confirmed by the greatest number of focuses of crustal earthquake in the LVZs [12].

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